

Requirements Prioritization in the Software Industry: Insights from a Practitioner Survey

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Survey Instrument: Requirements Prioritization in Software Projects

Personal and Professional Profile

1. Gender

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Other: _____

2. Education Level

- Incomplete Higher Education
- Completed Higher Education
- Incomplete Specialization/MBA
- Completed Specialization/MBA
- Incomplete Master's
- Completed Master's
- Incomplete Doctorate
- Completed Doctorate

3. Location

- Please provide the name of the city and the state abbreviation (e.g., Curitiba – PR):

4. Organization Size

- Micro (up to 19 employees)
- Small (up to 99 employees)
- Medium (up to 499 employees)
- Large (over 499 employees)
- Other: _____

5. What is your current position or role in your organization?

- Project Manager
- Product Manager
- Product Owner
- Scrum Master
- Business Analyst
- Domain Expert
- Requirements Analyst
- UX Designer
- Database Administrator
- Software Architect
- AI Engineer/Specialist
- Frontend Developer
- Backend Developer
- Fullstack Developer
- Mobile Developer
- Tester
- DevOps
- Data Scientist
- Other: _____

6. What is your experience in your current position?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 3 years
- 4 to 7 years
- 8 to 11 years
- 12 to 15 years
- Over 15 years
- Other: _____

7. Based on your current role, how would you classify your professional level?

- Junior
- Mid-level
- Senior
- I don't know
- Other: _____

Perception of the Requirements Prioritization Process

8. Which methodology is used in the software development process?

- Open-ended response: _____
9. Which technique(s) do you/your team currently use to prioritize requirements in software development projects?
- Open-ended response: _____

10. Please rate the importance of each criterion in the prioritization process (1 = Not important, 5 = Extremely important).

Criterion	1	2	3	4	5
Resource estimates	<input type="radio"/>				
Time estimates	<input type="radio"/>				
Cost	<input type="radio"/>				
Implementation complexity	<input type="radio"/>				
Dependence on other modules	<input type="radio"/>				
Customer needs	<input type="radio"/>				
Clarity in requirements	<input type="radio"/>				
Customer value	<input type="radio"/>				
Implementation risk	<input type="radio"/>				
Business goals	<input type="radio"/>				
Resource availability	<input type="radio"/>				
Technical feasibility	<input type="radio"/>				
Customer impact	<input type="radio"/>				

11. What are the main roles involved in the requirements prioritization process?

- Product Manager (Product Owner)
- Stakeholders
- Development Team
- Requirements Analyst
- Business Analyst
- End Users

- Scrum Master
- Project Manager
- Software Architects
- Quality Assurance Team
- Executives (Top Management)
- UX Designer
- UX Research
- Other: _____

12. Have you/your team ever used any prioritization technique based on Artificial Intelligence or Machine Learning? If so, which ones?

- Open-ended response: _____

13. What are the main challenges faced when applying prioritization techniques?

- Re-estimation of resources
- Impacts on architecture/data model
- Conflicting priorities
- Conflicting requirements
- Market changes
- Balancing multiple factors
- Managing stakeholder expectations
- Lack of communication
- Requirement changes
- Limited resources
- Tight schedules
- Difficulty differentiating essential from desirable requirements
- Limited use of techniques
- Other: _____

14. What are the main steps taken during the prioritization process?

- Identify and gather requirements
- Define evaluation criteria
- Assign weights/values
- Rank requirements
- Communication among stakeholders
- Regularly review priorities
- Identify dependencies and constraints
- Other: _____

15. In which phase of the project does prioritization occur?

- During the initial project planning phase
- During the prototyping phase
- During the requirements validation phase
- During the product backlog review
- During project development
- During the closure of each project phase
- After stakeholder feedback
- During the change management process
- At any time, as needed
- Before the release of new versions
- Other: _____

16. What types of scales does your team use to prioritize requirements?

- Nominal Scale
- Ordinal Scale
- Ratio Scale
- Qualitative Scale
- Other: _____

17. In your opinion, how does the use of techniques contribute to the prioritization process?

- Improves communication
- Increases transparency
- Improves resource allocation
- Facilitates adaptation to changes
- Ensures customer satisfaction
- Reduces project risks
- Improves schedule forecasting
- Speeds up the prioritization process
- Reduces conflicts
- Does not significantly contribute
- Other: _____

18. Are the available prioritization techniques effective in dealing with frequent requirement changes?

- Open-ended response: _____